

HOW TO CREATE EXCITEMENT IN BIG SIZE ENGLISH CLASSES AT HUFU

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ABSTRACT

As most language teachers are aware, excitement in classes is one of the most conducive things to learning. They also agree that teaching a small class of students is easier, more enjoyable, and less time consuming than teaching a large one. Leo Jones (2007) states: “The ideal size for a student-centered language class is probably 12!”. Unfortunately, they cannot choose the number of students in their classes. Due to budgets, space, or lack of teachers, many universities constantly offer big size classes which are like a lecture hall while the teachers’ job is not to lecture. As a result, creating excitement in big size classes is a major problem. It is difficult to keep all of students interested and participating with the goal of improving their communication skills. As a teacher has sustained that difficulty for nearly 12 years, I am eager to work on this study and try to find some effective ways of generating excitement in big size classes. The questionnaire was given to two English A1 classes. Interestingly, the survey gave students’ positive responses to teacher’s methods in classroom management, ESA sequence in teaching process and uses of some common visual aids which are available in a class. Hopefully, it will have a dramatic effect on language classes in my university (Ho Chi Minh City University of Food Industry).

Key words: crowded classes, a student-centered language class, teaching process, effective methods in classroom management.

1 INTRODUCTION

Do you find it easy to control and inspire classes getting bigger and bigger at your universities? How often do you find yourself out of time before coming close to accomplishing the daily learning objective? Ho Chi Minh City University is one of the key school training technical workers of the industry (with a focus on agricultural and food processing technology) for the region South. The university has 20 majors towards technology, accounting, business administration, commerce and tourism. English is a compulsory subject for all students for the first two years. After 3 or 4 modules, students are expected to be able to communicate in English, to read basic English documents and to discuss simple issues with foreigners in their fields. As the school size does not get along with the steadily increasing number of students, the classes have become overcrowded with students, sometimes almost filling the room, and exceed 40 people.

The problem is that it is too hard for teachers to motivate, inspire and interest students to the lesson. Most teachers seem to agree that there is no chance of getting so many students to learn. Leo Jones (2007) suggested the difficulty in reaching some students when a teacher circulates. Jeremy Harmer (2001) believed that it is impossible to organize dynamic and creative teaching and learning lesson.

There are a large number of methods for teaching a big-size class suggested by educators. Leo Jones (2007) indicated group arrangement and seating learners appropriately. Jeremy (2001) recommended some ways teachers can do such as using worksheets, using pair work and group work, apply chorus reaction, ect. Pratima D.S (2010) offered effective ways of using audio-visual aids in language teaching. Although much work has been carried out in terms of creating excitement in large classes, the maximum number of students is about 35, not 50 or 60 as most classes in HUFU. I have noticed that the question “How to create excitement in big size language classes” is posed in most specialized discussions. However, many teachers are still suffering.

The purpose of this study was to ascertain the effective language teaching methods which help teachers create an exciting and active atmosphere in English A1 and A2 classes in HUFU where the average number of students in a class is around 40. This topic was identified as being of important to teachers in providing them the necessary directions for creating excitement in big-size English A1-2 classes in HUFU.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 What is a big size class?

In some countries, 25-30 students per one teacher is considered large, while in other countries this is seen to be normal or even quite small. Actually a big size class has no “exact size.” Jeremy Harmer (2001) says: “Frequently, big classes mean that it is not easy to have students walking around or changing pairs etc.”. That is true, the easier students can move or change pairs or groups, the more interesting the classes become. Most of a teacher’s efforts to prepare a perfect and exciting lesson plans will surely be abortive only because his students keep getting stuck in their seats which are immovable.

2.2 Problems in big size classes

Obviously, in crowded classes both the teacher and students have a lot of difficulties.

Jeremy Harmer (2001) states: “In big classes, it is difficult for the teacher to make contact with the students at the back and it is difficult for the students to ask for and receive individual attention”. When teachers want to get feedback from students, some teachers only ask those in front desks and active ones to answer questions, hardly keep an eye to ones at the back or in the corner for some reasons such as time limited, difficulty in hearing, etc... Gradually, it seems to most students that the teacher is not interested in them; relationship between the teacher and students is not close. As a result they are not eager to participate in any classroom activities. Bad students always mean to sit as far from teacher as possible. They are not confident enough to

express their opinion or raise questions. Therefore, developing English skills in such big classes is impossible.

2.3 Solutions

First of all, classroom management is one of the burdensome responsibilities. According to Jeremy Harmer (2001), pair work and group work play an important part since they maximize student participation. In my own experience, in classes where tables cannot be moved students in the odd rows turn to face even rows. Teachers are advised to choose group leaders who can help to manage, encourage the members in group. For group-work organization, Penny Ur (1999) suggests: “The instructions that are given at the beginning are crucial”. If the students don’t know exactly what and how to do, there will be time-wasting, out of control and lack of effective practice. It is wise to give not only clear instructions but a specific sample before giving out materials to groups. The teachers’ job is to go from group to group to monitor, inspire and offer help in case of necessity.

Secondly, applying three elements of ESA of Jeremy Harmer (2001) in learning and teaching progress is one of the good ways to keep students involved in lessons. Explained clearly by Jeremy Harmer:

+ **E (Engage)**: This is the point in a teaching sequence where teachers try to arouse the students’ interest, thus involving their emotions.

+ **S (Study)**: *Study* activities are those where the students are asked to focus in on language (or information) and how it is constructed.

+ **A (Activate)**: This element describes exercises and activities which are designed to get students using language as freely as “communicatively” as they can.”

There are three types of sequence: ESA Straight Arrows sequence, EAS(A) Boomerang sequence and EAASAEA Patchwork sequence. As far as I am concerned, ESA Straight Arrow sequence best fits my classes in HUFI.

One activity sample described by Jeremy Harmer is that

+ **Engage**: Students and teacher look at a picture or video of modern robots. They say what the robots are doing. They say why they like or don’t like robots.

+ **Study**: The teacher shows students (the picture of) a particular robot. Students are introduced to “can” and “can’t” and say things like “It can do maths” and “It can’t play the piano”. The teacher tries to make sure the sentences are pronounced correctly and that the students use accurate grammar.

+ **Activate:** Students work in groups and design their own robot. They make a presentation to the class saying what their robot can and can't do.

Thirdly, all teachers of English believe that audio-visual aids are the best motivators. They are any device which can be used to make the learning experience more concrete, more realistic and more dynamic. They encourage students to work with more interest and real. As a result, audio-visual aids help learners understand the lessons more easily. Furthermore, they make the teachers' work more effective and interesting. According to Pratima Dave Shastri (2010), "These aids arouse the interest of the learners and motivate them to learn faster". For over many years, the list of language teaching aids has been added continuously. These are common types of them: textbooks, blackboard, maps, pictures, overhead projector, video, tape recorder, radio and television, computer and language games. In a typical classroom at HUFU, there are just some of them. Yet, I believe that if we know how to exploit their uses appropriately, the constant problems of creating excitement in big class will be solved.

- **Blackboard:** This is the first and foremost of all items of equipment. It must be there even if anything else is not there. It is the minimum equipment so it is easily available. In other words, blackboard is teacher's main support, sometimes it is considered as the second tongue of the teacher. However, there are some points teachers should pay attention to when using a blackboard. First, handwriting must be eligible. In a big class, it is hard for students at the back to read information written on the board if the letters are too small and written carelessly. Second, drawings should be visible. The teacher's purpose of transfer content of the lesson will fail if it's impossible to see and understand the drawings' meaning. Third, unwanted materials on the board should be rubbed off, otherwise they can distract students' attention to the point the teacher want to express. Finally, it is wise to combine white and multi-colored chalks which make your idea clearer.

- **Pictures:** I have heard that a picture speaks a thousand words. It , of course, doesn't mean words are less important than pictures. But the right picture at the right time at the right place is a great way to boost understanding as well as helping our students build memorable mental construction around a topic. It is advisable learner-centered approach should be used with pictures. For example, with the picture given by teacher, groups of students decide the guideline for discussion by themselves. They discuss the possibilities in the scene. After the time allowed, groups decide whose presentation is the best. In this activity, teachers should be a supervisor, supporter... They do not need to interfere with groups' discussions.

- **Videos:** In recent years, the use of video as an audio-visual material in language teaching has grown rapidly because of the increasing emphasis on communicative techniques and it is obvious that the use of video is a great help for language teachers i stimulating and facilitating the target language. Additionally, videos can motivate the learners, ensure their active viewing and participation and mix learning with enjoyment. With those outstanding advantages, videos are widely used to present new language items; Teacher can step in the process whenever he wishes: he can stop, start and rewind to repeat it for several times where necessary. Besides, students can concentrate on the language in detail and interpret what has been said, repeat it, predict the reply

and so on. Bryne (1981) states: "Video viewing has two purposes – it helps the students to predict and perform segments and try to comprehend meaning". Moreover, teacher can design group activities of language games which stimulates communication among students and helps to achieve communicative practice because students have an opportunity to develop sharing and cooperative skills. An important issue in this case is that the teacher should be careful with using and exploiting the video. Otherwise, it becomes complicated and purposeless for students.

- Language games: Pratima Dave Shastri (2010) suggests: "the language games should be introduced as they provide a welcome break in the learners' routine". Games have long been advocated for assisting language teaching. Because they add interest to what students might not find interesting and provide a context for meaningful communication as well as make learning challenging which take place as students seek to understand how to play the game and as they communicate about the game. Another important advantage is that games are student-centered and ensure total participation. Many games can be played in small groups, thereby providing a venue for students to develop the skills in working with others. In addition, students need variation to increase their motivation so games should be conducted in an enjoyable manner. Students can be involved in modifying and even creating games. However, learners have to following game rules which help to enhance discipline in the classroom. In addition, teachers need to pay attention to game difficulty level and students' ability. In other words, as a language teacher you should be creative.

3 METHODOLOGY

Motivating students in crowded English classes is really hard work for teachers of English. Two English A2 classes at HUFU, each consisting of about 40 students, were compared. They are from different majors but all have passed basic English with Face2Face course book. In these English A2 classes, most of them have finished English A1 with Life from Unit 1 to 6. The English A2 subject is also selected from the Life book – Elementary from Unit 7 to 12. Students in a class are divided into 6 groups with 5 or 7 persons each.

Since the present study focuses on the ways to create excitement in big size classes, it is important to elicit students' responses on classroom management, learning and teaching progress and the use of audio-visual resources in English 2 classes. Students were briefed that their responses are meant for research purposes and not related to their evaluation process. No personal identifying information was obtained. The students were informed that their participation in the study was voluntary.

A quantitative method was used to address and explore research questions. A questionnaire was designed to obtain students' feedback on solutions of boring atmosphere in big size English A2 classes at HUFU. It consists of 6 types of questions, each of which has from 2 to 5 options.

After the grammar lesson of Comparison in Unit 7B which was presented as ESA sequence. The questionnaires were distributed to all students in two English A2 classes which consist of 41 female students and 32 male students. The students had 15 minutes to choose the answers which indicate their subjective opinions about the ways the teacher, the researcher, has been conducting

during the course. Students were encouraged to seek researcher's help whenever they found a given question difficult to understand.

3.1 Comparison with ESA sequence.

+ **Engage:** Students and teacher look at a picture of 3 characters – The Princess, The Prince and Shrek – from a 2001 American computer-animated fantasy-comedy film. In groups, students write down as many describing adjectives about those characters as possible in 3 minutes. After allowed time, the teacher will collect and praise the group having the most adjectives.

+ **Study:** Students are introduced to short and long adjectives, comparative, superlative and equivalent. The teacher helps them to say things like “The Princess is taller than The Prince” and “The Prince is the shortest”, etc. The teacher tries to make sure the sentences are pronounced correctly and that the students use accurate grammar.

+ **Activate:** Students work in groups and write down as many comparison sentences about Shrek, The Princess and The Prince as possible in 10 minutes. They make a presentation to the class saying what they think of the 3 characters.

Questionnaire

This questionnaire is designed to help us understand your preferences regarding the ways to create excitement in big size English 1-2 classes at HUFİ. Participation depends on your willingness. No personal information should be written on the paper (name).

4 FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS

It seems to me that the purpose of the study which finds out the ways to excite learners in big size English classes has captured most students' concern. They were eager to answer the questions given. One hundred twenty seven students participated in the study. 56% was female students and 44% was male ones.

Figure 1: The number of years of studying English

The pie chart shows the number of years the students have been studying English. It is easily seen that most students – more than 80 percent of them - have had more than 5 years studying English which is an advantages for teacher of making the students understand the lessons. However, there are still 19 percent of students have studied English for less than 5 years. They can find it pretty difficult to keep in pace with their classmates who have more experience in practice English skills. It is advisable for teachers of English to get to know these students and spend more time for them in class.

Table 2: Response to working in groups

Group work can help you	Strongly agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
become more active in your learning	18% (13)	60% (43)	18% (13)	6% (4)
really understand the lesson	6% (4)	64% (47)	24% (22)	6% (4)
have more opportunities to learn in the style you like to	12% (9)	79% (57)	9% (7)	0
share ideas and question with others	72% (52)	19% (13)	12% (8)	0
develop the ability to apply knowledge and skills	7% (5)	43% (31)	22% (16)	28% (20)
feel a sense of personal responsibility for the success of a team	26% (19)	38% (28)	23% (17)	13% (9)

The table indicates how students respond to working in groups in a large class. It can be clearly seen that most of them agree on benefits they get from working with others.

More than 50 percent of students appreciate the advantages stated. Group work can help them become more active which helps students learn, not simply to occupy their time. In groups, with supports from other members they can understand the lesson more easily because some students are too shy to ask their teacher for help. Moreover, students can learn in a style they like. Some prefer using pictures, images, and spatial understanding or sound and music. Others prefer study words, both in speech and writing. Members in a group may have different perspectives and creative learning styles, and so the group may come up with more varied and imaginative ways.

It comes to our attention that the majority of students strongly agree that working in groups, they can share ideas and question with others. It is true that by listening to how others solve their issues, they may get further ideas on how to solve their own issues and the group may have varied views on how to represent some ideas, however this is a positive part of learning in groups.

In addition, working in groups to practice behaviors or procedures help students understand their role as well as responsibilities for the success of a team. No one, of course, want to fall behind or be looked down on. As a result, most of them try their best to be an important factor in their own groups.

However, half of participants doubt their ability to apply knowledge and skills. As we can learn from the table that more than 20 percent of students doesn't get any benefits from group working. About 30 percent of them still consider it hard to understand lessons and feel that they have no responsibility for their group's achievements. Even several students become passive and count to their friends. Also, different personalities and learning styles can be a barrier for them to feel pleased to work with others.

Grammar - COMPARISON

Figure 3a: Grammar Lesson “Comparison” with ESA sequence teaching method - With FEMALE students

Grammar - COMPARISON

Figure 3b: Grammar Lesson “Comparison” with ESA sequence teaching method -
With MALE students

Besides, more than two thirds of students expressed their own opinion about group work with the question “Other opinions”. It is interesting to know that studying with others help them understand the benefits of collaborative learning. They have a free-studying environment to ask, to get support from other members in group which is useful for their homework. However, students work best together if they know or trust each other, at least to some extent. Still, some hold that some members tend to lead and control the group which makes them uncomfortable or demotivated to join group’s activities.

The pie chart shows satisfaction levels of female and male students about the grammar lesson of Comparison in English 2 subject. Obviously, there is a big difference between two genders of student. Female learners are more interested in the lesson than male ones.

From figure 3a more than 90 percent female students are excited about the lesson. Only 9 percent of them like the lesson a little. From figure 3b nearly half of female learners like the lesson little and 8 percent of them find it boring. That means more than fifty percent of male students are not interested in the lesson.

With the option “Others”, students offer some more following information. Some of them felt excited about the lesson but because of the shortage of vocabulary it was difficult for them to keep up the lesson.

Luckily no one find the lesson very boring

Table 4: The necessary of audio and visual aids in English classes

Question	Response	Score	Percentage
<i>Do you find the use of audio and visual aids in English classes necessary?</i>	Yes	56	77
	No	17	23

Table 1 shows that most of the students find the need for the English teachers to use audio-visual aids in the classroom. However, 23% did not find the need for the English teachers to use audio-visual aids in the classroom. This indicates that there are students who find the audio-video teaching sessions not very necessary in the English language classroom.

Students gave interesting responses to this question. Some students hold that “students cannot understand the lesson in traditional ways but using audio-visual aids will help them to get the teacher’s explanation better”. Other opinions related to improving English language skills by reducing the number of students in a class, listening to native speakers and adding more interesting activities to practice English. Students also felt that audio-visual aids can be useful when teachers find certain language terms difficult to explain on the white boards.

Few students are of the opinion that teachers need not use audio-visual aids in the classroom. A student opined “that’s because the teacher doesn’t translate some difficult term”. These students are of the opinion that teachers can make clear the idea by translating without using audio-visual aids in the classroom. These students seem to be comfortable with traditional methods of teaching.

Figure 5: Visual aids for each step of ESA sequence

The chart shows students’ preference for the use of visual aids for each step of ESA sequence. As we can see from the chart there is a clear prominence of each kind of aids when applying ESA sequence into lessons.

Firstly, in the step of “Engage” about 45 percent of students enjoy watching video relating to the lesson. The second preferred choice is pictures – more than 20 percent. The least attracting aid is blackboard. The students probably love watching something active, colorful and funny at the beginning of a class.

Secondly, power point teaching technique is the highest in the step “Study”– higher than a traditional blackboard by 20%. Students may believe that with a power point lesson plan which is full of effects, a teacher can make his/her teaching more comprehensive. However, a blackboard is not the most common choice as the power point, though, it is still higher than the rest. This can be understood that a traditional blackboard is always an essential thing in class. Furthermore, some students suggested that teachers should be flexible in the way they make the lesson understood. In other words, a teacher should combine different kinds of aid in the second step which is considered as the most important part of a teacher’s lesson plan.

Thirdly, it’s not a surprise when language game outstrips the others in the final step, “Activate”. Maybe before ending a class, students would like to do something relaxing but competitive with their mates. However, there are also some requests that games, like any other activities or tools, shouldn’t be overused since when they are exploited too much, the motivating element disappears rapidly. In addition, when the game is very exciting, students tend to use the mother tongue. Because of the natural urge to win, they may cheat.

5 DISCUSSION

Creating excitement in big size classes is a challenging task because teachers need to keep students’ interest as well as engage them in the learning process. Some think it is impossible to motivate students in a crowded class. The findings, however, has opened a road which can help.

Firstly, the way of putting students in the groups works well in classroom management. As a teacher, I find it easier to control their present in class. Students tend to be more active because the majority of them feel a sense of personal responsibility for the success of a team. They can share their opinions, experience with other members. Some said that it was interesting to teach others what they know which helps them remember and understand the lesson more.

Secondly, applying ESA sequence into teaching process made most of students concentrate better. However, the findings shows the difference of 2 genders’ attention. I had an interview with some boys after the survey. They claimed that the Princess, the Prince and Shrek in the picture didn’t encourage them to talk and think. They wanted some picture with characters who were more famous and attractive. The lesson can be said to be successful, though, as a teacher we should consider carefully about choosing teaching aids which are able to capture learners’ interest.

Thirdly, most participants admitted the necessity of audio-visual aids. The findings indicate some following main points:

- + Engage: Videos seem engage the students quickly. They like watching interesting clips relating to the lesson. To avoid boredom of exploit videos so much, teachers can integrate them with pictures and language games. Those can be an effective warming-up way.
- + Study: Although power point lesson got the most preference, students find it in combination with blackboard and pictures useful in understanding difficult concepts given in the course books. It is true because the majority of students come from countryside. They didn’t have

many opportunities to practice English skills, they are familiar with tradition translation. Therefore, the more flexible we are in using visual aids, the more we meet the variety of students' levels.

- + Activate: The findings states that language games must be the first choice for teacher to end a class. They can inspire students, attract them into class activities. Because they are aware of their own contribution to their group's winning. Furthermore, games increase groups' solidarity and help students become closer.

Regardless of the other small number of choices though, I am satisfied with positive responses from students. I feel that putting students into groups, applying ESA sequence and combining audio-visual aids flexibly can be effective ways to improve the motivation of students, thus improving the student work. I am confident that in the future I can increase the productivity of my students.

This research aims students in English A2 classes. A further one for specific purpose (ESP) is needed because there is a limitation of reference source. A large number of learners often get bored in ESP classes and seem not eager to come to class. The similar research can be conducted with students whose majors are accounting or tourist. Because it is easier to find supporting resources, in the market it is not difficult to find a course book or videos for those majors. Furthermore, the language for them is heard every day on radio or television.

6 CONCLUSION

To sum up, crowded classes have brought about a lot of problems to teachers as well as students. The issue of creating excitement in big size classes at HUFU is one of the difficulties most of teachers are facing. However, I believe that having good ways of managing classroom, applying appropriately ESA sequence and combining creatively audio-visual aids in teaching, teachers will be able to make their teaching effective and class atmosphere exciting.

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f. Others:

5. Do you find the use of audio and visual aids in English classes necessary?

a. Yes b. No

+ Reason:

6. Which visual aids do you prefer for each step of ESA sequence?

Aids	Engage	Study	Activate
Blackboard			
Pictures			
Video			
Power point			
Language games			

Other opinions:

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